

COVID-19 and the digitized transformation of the Health & Medical sector: an era of uncertainty

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to examine how the role of IT has changed in the Health & Medical sector due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This was done by considering three prominent IT aspects: IT governance, business process integration and cybersecurity risk management. In order to give more concrete advice on business process integration and cybersecurity, we specifically focus on the process of telemedicine. By studying the outcomes of various academic studies, we propose improvements in these three areas in order to facilitate an effective digital transformation. We find that digital transformation has become an increasingly important factor for the survival of an organization, where acceleration of adaptation is key.

Keywords

Digital transformation, Health & Medical, IT governance, COVID-19, resilience, Cyber security, Business process integration

1. INTRODUCTION

For the first time in the 21st century, a global health pandemic demonstrates the world's global economy how vulnerable healthcare and the economy have become. Especially the hospitals within the Health & Medical sector have had a major impact during the COVID-19 outbreak earlier this year. An article on the impact of COVID-19 says that the outbreak has taken a huge toll on healthcare professionals, particularly in developed countries like the United States, France and Spain. Patients with other conditions are having delays on surgeries with doctors and nurses working non-stop to help beat the virus. Also, the lack of liquidity, administrative and overloaded IT systems are causing delays as well (Journal of mHealth, 2020). These are short term consequences that the healthcare sector had to endure. Aside from the extraordinary impact on society and business as a

whole. The increased anxiety caused the likelihood of cyber-attacks succeeding corresponding with an increase in the number and range of cyber-attacks (Lallie et al., 2020). The pandemic also catalyzed rapid adoption of telehealth and changes in decision making. To provide the entire spectrum of activities used to deliver care at a distance (Wosik et al., 2020).

Therefore, this paper is written with the purpose of illustrating several implications based on IT governance, business process changes and cybersecurity risks that COVID-19 caused within the healthcare sector. In addition, the IST and SOLL situation will be analyzed based on the mentioned implications within the healthcare sector. To eventually provide a clear overview of the impact COVID-19 caused on these subjects.

2. OBJECTIVE

The COVID-19 pandemic has forced many organisations to change their way of working, and the role of IT has become increasingly important. Many industries are forced to undergo a rapid digital transformation, and the Health & Medical sector is no exception. The importance of digital transformation in this sector has been emphasized for a while, with Coile (2000) noting that “the Internet is the next frontier of healthcare” (p. 8). The pandemic could be seen as an extra incentive to speed up this process. However, this is not an easy task as it considerably changes some of the processes in this sector. The aim of this paper is to examine the digital transformation in the Health & Medical sector due to COVID-19. We will first look at the IT governance of hospitals, and then focus on the process of telemedicine in the contexts of business process integration as well as cybersecurity. Based on this analysis, we answer our research question: “How did COVID-19 affect the role of IT within the Health & Medical sector?”.

3. APPROACH

This research is performed through a literature study. Literature from different sources from before and after the COVID-19 pandemic are compared to look for any changes. Among these sources are academic studies as well as company annual reports. The goal of this study is to create knowledge and new insights to better understand how COVID-19 has led to digital transformation of organizations in the healthcare sector. The current role of IT in the healthcare industry will be analyzed and discussed, with a particular focus on IT governance, processes and risk.

4. HEALTH & MEDICAL

Even though the pandemic had a major impact on organizations across sectors (McKinsey & Company, 2020), this paper will primarily focus on the Health & Medical sector. The Health & Medical sector consists of businesses that provide medical services, manufacture medical equipment or drugs, provide medical insurance, or otherwise facilitate the provision of healthcare to patients (Chappelow, 2020).

The global healthcare market reached a value of nearly \$8,452 billion in 2018, and was expected to grow to \$11,908.9 billion by 2022 (Business Wire, 2019). According to the World Health Organization (2019) roughly 6.6% of the gross domestic product (GDP) was globally spent on healthcare in 2017. This makes the Health & Medical sector one of the largest industries.

Compared to other industries, the Health & Medical sector distinguishes itself by its highly regulated nature. These regulations stem from the fundamental concerns that are at stake since vulnerable factors, like life and health, are involved (Field, 2008). This results in a number of provisions that apply specifically to information technology targeted at the Health & Medical sector, like the US' Health Information Technology for Economic and Clinical Health (HITECH) Act. Confidentiality is also vital to any medical exchange, because of the sensitive data processed by these information systems.

4.1 Pre-COVID19

The Health & Medical sector were arguably in an uncertain situation before the outbreak of the COVID-19 virus. According to Deloitte (2019), this uncertainty was caused by the emergence of personalized medicine, exponential technologies, disruptive competitors, expanded delivery sites and revamped payment models. Organizations were expected to make future moves to remain relevant and financially viable.

The increase in market value directly correlated to an escalation in expenditures, limiting the produced revenue. This growth in expenditure varies by region/country but is likely caused by the increase of life expectancy, growing populations and technological advances.

4.2 Post-COVID19

The Health & Medical professionals have been on the front-line ever since the outbreak due to the rapidly increasing number of health emergencies caused by the COVID-19 virus. Alongside the direct medical help, many research laboratories rapidly redistributed resources to start researching potential medication and vaccines (Lurie et al., 2020, p. 1972). The global demand for respiratory equipment grew, prompting the production side of the sector to meet this demand. Nearly all sides of the sector were impacted in some way by the outbreak.

This prompted a significant digital transformation within the sector, resulting in accelerated digital innovation and integration of new technologies to meet the demand (McCay, 2020). For example, information technology was deployed to streamline the evaluation and identification of cases to improve efficiency (Budd et al., 2020, p. 1184). Another example is Telemedicine, the use of digital information and communication technologies to remotely manage health care, which quickly became the new norm (Bestsenyy, 2020).

Information technology has become an enabler for many organizations throughout the Health & Medical sector, and has had an important role in a comprehensive response to the outbreak.

5. ANALYSIS

This analysis will focus on the effects of the COVID19 outbreak on the Health & Medical sector from three different perspectives: IT Governance and Strategic Sourcing, Business Process Integration and Cyber Security. To be able to explore these perspectives in an appropriate level of detail, this analysis will mainly examine the adjusted situation within hospitals.

For each of these perspectives the digital situation pre-COVID19 and the transformed digital situation post-COVID19 will be analyzed and compared, to examine the digital transformation the sector has gone through.

5.1 IT Governance and Strategic Sourcing

To get an accurate representation of the exact changes that were made to the IT governance of hospitals, a baseline shall be established. To form this baseline, the pre-COVID19 situation will be examined first.

5.1.1 Pre-COVID19

The rise in complexity and sophistication of the IT capability in hospitals has increased the importance of IT governance within these organizations (Bradley et al., 2012, p. 156). Research by Burke et al. (2008) suggested that IT governance matters to a hospital's financial performance, showing the most positive outcomes for hospitals where the CIO reports to the CFO. To classify the selected IT governance structure of hospitals, the Governance Design Matrix developed by Weill and Ross (Weill 2004; Weill and Ross 2005, 2004) will be used to illustrate 'who' is responsible for decisions, and its corresponding results.

As reported by multiple papers, there is an apparent scarcity of literature that considers the antecedents of IT governance within health care (Bradley et al., 2012, p. 167; Köbler et al., 2010, p. 359). That is why an applicable quantitative empirical survey on the IT decision makers in German Hospitals (Köbler et al., 2010; Köbler et al., 2009) will be used to provide insight of IT governance generalized to western hospitals. The research is based on 203 survey results from IT executives of German hospitals, collected through a standardized online questionnaire. When looking at the division in decision domains, significant differences can be found between small-sized hospitals (1-199 beds), medium-sized hospitals (200-799 beds) and large-sized hospitals (800+ beds). This is why the results are segmented into these three categories.

IT Principles

The IT principles domain is described as the collection of high-level decisions about the strategic role of IT in the business. Table 1 shows that the federal archetype, the most common archetype in this decision area (36,0%), increases with the hospital size while the IT duopoly decreases with the size.

Table 1. Decision area: IT Principles

	1-199 beds (N = 40)	200-799 beds (N = 130)	800+ beds (N = 33)	Total (N =203)
Business Monarchy	10,0%	9,2%	9,1%	9,3%
IT Monarchy	25,0%	24,6%	27,3%	25,1%
Feudal*	-	-	-	-
Federal	25,0%	36,2%	48,5%	36,0%
IT Duopoly	32,5%	25,4%	12,1%	24,6%
Anarchy*	-	-	-	-

* = These results were not completely deductible from Köbler et al.'s research.

IT Architecture

The IT architecture includes an integrated set of technical choices to guide the organization in satisfying business needs. Table 2 shows that the majority of hospitals choose to let the IT monarchy archetype (71,9%) decide on this domain, likely due to its technically-driven nature.

Table 2. Decision area: IT Architecture

	1-199 beds (N = 40)	200-799 beds (N = 130)	800+ beds (N = 33)	Total (N =203)
Business Monarchy*	5,0%	-	-	-
IT Monarchy	65,0%	70,0%	87,9%	71,9%
Feudal*	-	-	-	-
Federal*	12,5%	9,3%	-	-
IT Duopoly	15,0%	15,3%	6,1%	13,7%
Anarchy*	-	-	-	-

* = These results were not completely deductible from Köbler et al.'s research.

IT Infrastructure Strategies

The IT infrastructure consists of the centrally coordinated, shared IT services that provide the foundation for the enterprise's IT capability. In table 3 a preference can be recognized for the IT monarchy archetype (56,2%), particularly for larger hospitals (66,7%).

Table 3. Decision area: IT Infrastructure Strategies

	1-199 beds (N = 40)	200-799 beds (N = 130)	800+ beds (N = 33)	Total (N =203)
Business Monarchy*	5,0%	0,8%	-	-
IT Monarchy	50,0%	55,4%	66,7%	56,2%
Feudal*	-	-	-	-
Federal	22,5%	10,8%	15,2%	13,8%
IT Duopoly	17,5%	33,1%	15,2%	27,1%
Anarchy*	-	-	-	-

* = These results were not completely deductible from Köbler et al.'s research.

Business Application Needs

Business application needs are the business requirements for purchased or internally developed IT applications. Table 4 shows more of a division over almost all archetypes, contrary to what can be seen in the other domains. The IT duopoly is the most common (36,4%).

Table 4. Decision area: **Business Application Needs**

	1-199 beds (N = 40)	200-799 beds (N = 130)	800+ beds (N = 33)	Total (N =203)
Business Monarchy	27,5%	24,6%	9,1%	22,7%
IT Monarchy	17,5%	10,8%	21,2%	13,8%
Feudal	5,0%	-	-	-
Federal	12,5%	13,1%	15,2%	13,3%
IT Duopoly	32,5%	36,9%	39,4%	36,4%
Anarchy	5,0%	10,8%	12,1%	9,9%

** = These results were not deductible from Köbler et al.'s research.*

IT Investment

IT investment decisions determine how much and where an organization invests in IT. Table 5 shows that the federal and IT duopoly archetypes dominate primarily. Especially within larger hospitals the federal archetype is the most common (39,4%).

Table 5. Decision area: **IT Investment**

	1-199 beds (N = 40)	200-799 beds (N = 130)	800+ beds (N = 33)	Total (N =203)
Business Monarchy	20,0%	14,6%	15,2%	15,8%
IT Monarchy	15,0%	11,5%	21,2%	13,8%
Feudal	10,0%	4,6%	-	-
Federal	32,5%	31,5%	39,4%	33,0%
IT Duopoly	20,0%	31,5%	24,2%	28,0%
Anarchy	-	-	-	-

** = These results were not deductible from Köbler et al.'s research.*

5.1.2 Post-COVID19

In 2019, a survey by Price Waterhouse Cooper revealed that 38% of executives of U.S. healthcare

systems reported that they had not incorporated digital into their corporate strategies (PwC Health Research Institute, 2019). The same report also stressed the importance of the integration of products and services via a digital transformation. Now, during the times of COVID-19, this has become especially crucial. Whitelaw et al. (2020) found that countries who have quickly deployed digital technologies have remained ahead of the curve. Regulations about digital technologies are also changing. For example, in the U.S., Congress has lifted provisions that limited the use of telemedicine in rural areas (Keesara et al., 2020).

Adopting these technologies needs to be well organized. The IT governance of hospitals should be changed according to these new challenges and requirements. New technologies can be complex, and it can be difficult to incorporate them into your business' needs. Ting et al. (2020) discuss the potential applications of technologies such as big-data analytics, artificial intelligence and blockchain. Since some of these can become quite technical, IT managers are vital in identifying appropriate technologies for business needs. The main issue that hospitals face right now is to make the required changes to achieve an effective digital transformation. Not only this, but the implementation also needs to be quick in order to deal with the extra demands during the pandemic. To facilitate this, it is imperative that the IT governance structure supports this challenging endeavor. It is important that IT decision-making is in line with enterprise objectives, but in this specific COVID-19 crisis it is more crucial to go digital quickly, while still ensuring that current processes do not experience any downsides or delays.

5.2 Business process integration

The COVID-19 outbreak caused a major digital transformation for companies and their processes. This pandemic forced companies to adapt their processes to the environment, but also for specific changes in the business needs. Especially in the Health & Medical sector where hospitals are standing in the frontline for fighting the coronavirus. In this paragraph, the changes in the hospital processes are examined and analyzed. In this paragraph the differences between telemedicine and a normal consultation will be discussed using UML activity diagrams.

According to Bokolo telemedicine should be adopted as a proactive measure to improve medical care and should not only be seen as a temporary fix in times of emergency; rather, it is a convenient, safe, scalable, effective, and green method of providing medical care. One of the major changes in the day to day healthcare services is the attendance

of “telemedicine”. According to Ohannessian, Duong & Odone the outbreak response strategy included early diagnosis, patient isolation, symptomatic monitoring of contacts, as well as suspected and confirmed cases, and a public health quarantine. The confinement of population and the outbreak impact on health care systems is disrupting routine care for non COVID-19 patients. Telemedicine, particularly video consultations, has been promoted and scaled up during the pandemic to reduce the transmission, especially in the United States of America and the United Kingdom (Ohannessian, Duong & Odone, 2020).

According to Portnoy, Waller & Elliot, healthcare professionals must take appropriate measures to ensure that individuals with low-risk diseases, as well as the “worried well”, do not take up the already limited healthcare resources while ensuring that those who are seriously ill receive appropriate triage and treatment. That is the reason why telemedicine can help prevent the overload in the hospitals and stimulates the decrease in the amount of infections. The authors also describe Telemedicine as the potential to help by permitting mildly ill patients to get the supportive care they need while minimizing their exposure to other acutely ill patients (Portnoy, Waller & Elliot, 2020).

The introduction of telemedicine during the COVID-19 outbreak is one of the major process changes for the Health & Medical sector.

The following models present the consult process in hospitals before and after the COVID-19 pandemic.

Figure 1: Model of the consult process before the COVID-19 pandemic

Figure 2: Model of the consulting process after the COVID-19 pandemic

The most notable changes of the telemedicine process are related to the fact that both the health care take and the health care provider must log in to the system to initiate a remote connection. This connection is verified by a server. The report from Bokolo concludes that technological advances in telemedicine have proven to possess huge potential in supporting social distancing and quarantine towards controlling the spread COVID-19. An additional benefit as described by Okereafor et al is that remote consults can be recorded. This allows medical consults to have a second opinion by another doctor so that they can share their experience and knowledge. Doctors can collaborate about their findings using telemedicine. Furthermore, it is a possibility that the prescribed medicines are delivered to the patient via a postal service. The patient does not need to pick-up the medicines at their local pharmacy to reduce physical contact and crowded areas. The information and instructions provided about how to use the medicines can be given by an employee from the pharmacy for example by telephone.

5.3 Cybersecurity

The shift in use of technology for telemedicine has caused changes in the processes and activities for the health and medical sector. These changes bring some risks and consequences relating to cybersecurity. In this paragraph the risks relating to telemedicine will be discussed through a risk analysis. First we will identify the risks that are applicable to telemedicine and then the impact and

likelihood of these risks will be discussed as well as how the risk relates to the CIA triad.

The following risks are identified for telemedicine in the health and medical sector:

- Data leak of sensitive information;
- Service being unavailable;
- Susceptibility to man-in-the-middle attacks (e.g. eavesdropping);
- Misinterpretations (e.g. non-verbal observations);
- Lack of control over the collection, use and sharing of data;
- Phishing;
- Possible recordings would contain very sensitive information.

The first risk relates to confidentiality. A data leak of sensitive information can happen in various ways, but hospitals usually protect their patients' data very well because they could face repercussions if they fail to safeguard the data. Normally, we could say the likelihood of a data leak is low. Due to the digital transformation and increased use of telemedicine because of COVID-19, however, there are some new technologies being used. This also increases the likelihood of a data leak to moderate.

The second risk relates to availability. Hospitals that choose to do online consultations will have to use one of these 3rd party applications. Because these providers know what they are doing, the service becoming unavailable has a low likelihood. Nevertheless, if there is an issue with the online consultation platform, there is no other option to go with, and the patient is stuck at home without getting their health assessment. This means that if the service is unavailable, the impact is very high.

The third risk relates to confidentiality. Since online consultations are done across an online video communications platform, it is not unthinkable that someone gains access and eavesdrops on the conversation. The likelihood of this happening is actually quite low as most platforms already have security in place for this, but it can still happen from time to time. The impact of a man-in-the-middle attack is classified as high, since it is a breach of personal data, leading to reputational and regulatory issues for the hospital. In comparison with risk 1, data leak of sensitive information, the impact is slightly smaller since the personal data is only leaked to the attacker, who then decides what to do with it.

The fourth risk relates to integrity. Misinterpretation, while impacting the integrity of the information transmitted, does not impact the provided care too significantly. Misinterpretation of observations is likely to occur more often, especially when the technology on the client's end is of lesser quality. This can lead to incorrect diagnosis or

treatment. The miscommunicated information tends to be minor, while bigger, more significant observations will often be observed correctly. That is why it received a lower impact-score.

The fifth risk relates to confidentiality. Depending on the exact sensors offered to the patient, the likelihood and impact of this risk increase in severity. It is likely that the data transmitted by the patient's sensors will contain irrelevant information to the health care professionals. The impact is positively correlated by the sensitivity of this data, increasing as the data is more sensitive. If not sensitive, the impact of this risk can be very low. Sensitive data can be misused by parties and used to deduct personal details about the patient.

The sixth risk relates to confidentiality. Phishing for credentials can be achieved by sending false emails or telephone calls to a victim, which believes it is from a genuine party. The victim might trust the sender and provide authentication information such as login names and passwords. The likelihood that this happens is classified as moderate since phishing attempts occur on a daily basis. The phishing attempt would only succeed if the victim actually provides the needed information for a hack. The impact of this risk would be moderate as the phisher might be able to obtain sensitive information which they can use for identity theft or extortion.

The last risk relates to confidentiality. The leakage of information from customers has a high likelihood because there are many methods which can cause a data breach. For example when a hacker hacks into the storage system where the recordings are stored and steals the data. This leaked out data can be used to extort patients. In that case the impact is high.

6. DISCUSSION

6.1 Business process integration

One of the major process changes within the Health & Medical sector is telemedicine. The online patient consultation is integrated worldwide and helps standard patients care in this corona era. It is difficult to give advice on how these processes can and must change or how long telemedicine would prevail in these times. This can only be analyzed in a post-crisis situation. According to the Luxembourg Institute of health the following conclusions are right regarding the current telemedicine situation:

1. A sizable proportion of outpatient visits in various settings can be clinically managed effectively from a distance, that is, patients with non-urgent conditions can be triaged to telemedicine service without

- compromising their health or quality of care.
2. The requisite infrastructure for connectivity is widely available at both ends of the clinical encounter, most readily through the ubiquitous smartphone. Most health care systems in private and public sectors have already deployed electronic health records, thereby ensuring continuity of care for their patients.
 3. The necessary logistics can be developed promptly, including the necessary training where needed, staffing and work flow with minimal disruptions or dislocations.
 4. Little or no resistance can be encountered to this modality of care delivery since it is protective for providers and patients.
 5. Government has relaxed all restrictive regulations for telemedicine deployment, including interstate licensing, data confidentiality issues, and most significantly reimbursement (Bashshur, Doarn & Frenk, 2020).

6.2 IT Governance and Strategic Sourcing

In a rapidly changing environment where IT decisions need to be made quickly, moving IT decision jurisdiction toward a more centralized model can accelerate the adaptation of new technology (McElheran, 2012, p. 29). In times of uncertainty and chaos, this shift can help facilitate rapid request response (Xue, Ray, & Gu, 2011, p. 390). Due to the required digital transformation, shifting to a more IT-centered governance pattern can be effective short-term. Once the digital transformation has matured, and required changes have been made, the archetypes can be restored to a more stable governance pattern.

In the proposed governance pattern, IT Investment, which is often governed by the Federal archetype, can be moved to IT Duopoly or IT Monarchy to achieve centralization. The decision area of IT business application needs would also benefit from moving toward a governance archetype with heavier responsibility from the IT side. All other decision areas can continue to function properly with the current most practiced governance types. To reiterate: IT architecture and infrastructure can use an IT monarchy, while IT principles can remain being governed by the federal archetype.

6.3 Cybersecurity

We have previously introduced and analyzed several risks involved with the adoption of telemedicine for hospitals. To minimize the risks identified, we have proposed several improvements

(strong authentication, data encryption, connection encryption, negotiating availability and data erasure). The security concerns need to be dealt with quickly in order for doctors and patients to safely use the telemedicine services. Prioritization of these improvement measures and a clear strategy are essential (Perakslis, 2014). Since most measures are quite technical, heavy involvement from the IT department is necessary. Most C-level executives do not have the technical expertise necessary to quickly make decisions regarding cybersecurity improvements. This is in line with our findings that the IT governance of hospitals needs to head in a more IT-centered direction, especially in the short term. Long term, however, it becomes increasingly important that senior management is more engaged with cybersecurity, from planning to implementation (Abraham, Chatterjee & Sims, 2019). This way, cybersecurity can be properly integrated into the organization's strategy, and further improvements and changes to the cyber-risk mitigation measures can be made.

7. CONCLUSION

This research serves as a general starting point for mapping the changes that were induced to the role of IT within the Health & Medical sector, caused by the COVID-19 outbreak. The digital transformation was examined from three different perspectives, each with their own approach and corresponding findings.

Unfortunately, due to the recent nature of the virus, there is a limited selection of literature available on the exact impact on the selected three perspectives. For this research, the lack of literature was mainly noticeable in observing the changes in IT governance after the COVID-19 outbreak. With limited data it is also difficult to forecast approaching changes and roadblocks, making it challenging to apply existing literature on the uncertain, rapidly changing situation.

The current virus outbreak provides many new insights on the resilience of organizations worldwide. Therefore we would encourage further research and data collection on the exact effects of the COVID-19 outbreak on the IT within the Health & Medical sector. Collecting more data through primary data collection can provide new insights on the matter, especially after some more time has passed and some organizations mature their digital transformation even further. These findings can be analyzed to examine how changes within the IT impact the Health & Medical organization, and thus help improve these organizations to become more resilient against threats of uncertainty.

In general, this research has shown us that digital transformation is vital to the survival of organizations. Not only in the Health & Medical

sector, but across all sectors. The acceleration of adaptation has been the deciding factor for a lot of organizations during the global health outbreak.

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